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A discrete Schrodinger model that describes the quantum measurement process

Hiroki Yagisita (Kyoto Sangyo University)

We propose a discrete Schrodinger model that describes the quantum measurement process.

Let X be the Hilbert space of state vectors of a one-particle system of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ on the one-dimensional discrete grid \mathbb{Z} . That is, $X = L^2(\mathbb{Z}; \mathbb{C}^2)$. Let natural numbers L_0 and N_0 be very large. Put $I = \{n \in \mathbb{Z} | L_0 \leq |n| \leq L_0 + N_0\}$. We assume that I is **the place where two detectors exist**.

Suppose that for $n \in I$, $V(n)$ is a 2×2 Hermitian **random matrix**. Suppose that for $n \in I$, if U is a 2×2 unitary matrix, then the distributions of $(U^{-1})(V(n))U$ and $V(n)$ are the same. Suppose that for $n \in I$, the density function of $V(n)$, roughly speaking, is smooth and compact supported. Suppose that $\{V(n)\}_{n \in I}$ is independent and identically distributed.

Suppose that for $n \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus I$, $V(n)$ is the 2×2 **zero matrix**.

Then, we propose a discrete Schrodinger model

$$\sqrt{-1} \frac{du}{dt}(n) = -\frac{1}{2m}((u(n-1) - u(n)) + (u(n+1) - u(n))) + V(n)u(n)$$

on the Hilbert space $X(= L^2(\mathbb{Z}; \mathbb{C}^2))$.

continuous spontaneous localization, objective-collapse theory, quantum decoherence, quantum entanglement, quantum information, Anderson localization, CHSH inequality, Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox.

<https://arxiv.org/abs/0807.3612>